

Answer ALL questions:

Q. Complete the following sentences:

- 1. A Is a group of words that does not have a subject or a verb or neither a subject nor verb.**
- 2. A strong or good paragraph should have and**
- 3. Every topic sentence should have and**
- 4. Examples of coordinators are and**
- 5. An example of descriptive adjectives is friendly, for example**
- 6. Brainstorming by listing means**
- 7. Adjectives can come before nouns, e.g. or after verbs to be or senses verb**
- 8. In titles, all words should be capitalized except , , , and**
- 9. Concluding sentences are of four types. They can 1., 2., 3. and 4.**

Q.2 Is this paragraph good or bad? And why?

I had a really bad dream yesterday. I felt bad when I woke up. The drive to work took a long time, and it was so depressing. When I finally go to work, my boss was in a bad mood. Work was just really stressful the whole day. I left to go home later, and I didn't feel like staying at home. I called some people and they were all rude to me. I ended up just doing a stuff around the house. I watched some stuff on TV and fell asleep during a boring show.

Q.3 Develop the following topics to write good topic sentences:

a. Global warming

There are many possible contributing factors to global warming.

b. Dogs

Dogs make wonderful pets because they help you to live longer.

Al- Salam University College
English Department
Fourth Class
Subject: Transformational Grammar

2016/ 2017
Final Exam
Time: 3 Hours
Teacher: Alhan Tariq

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Identify the three schools of Grammar and clarify the differences among them. (10 Marks)

Q.2 Draw tree diagrams of the following sentences: (10 Marks)

1. Yes, Murphy has been very quiet.
2. The fireman will be having trouble soon.

Q.3 A. Use features to explain why the following sentences are ungrammatical. Then correct the sentences. (Five only)(10 Marks)

1. *The perseverance is a virtue.
2. *He has read book.
3. *Despair dropped to the floor.
4. *The eagle prayed for an hour.
- 5.* My boss elapsed.
- 6.* We vanished the spot.

B. What are the three components of Transformational Grammar? Explain.

Q.4 Transform the following sentences into surface structures using tree diagrams: (10 Marks)

1. not she present look tired
2. not Mary past be friendly
3. not they present have seen me here
4. not no that cat present resemble my sister's cat

Q.5 Answer either A or B of the following question: (10 Marks)

A. 1. Give the deep structure from which the following sentence is derived:

What could the man have been doing?

2. From the deep structure, give the words that are represented by the following symbols:

Aux1, V, M, be, Aux, MV, VP

B. Give the surface structure using a tree diagram and applying the transformations, if applicable, in the order: 1) negative, 2) yes no 3) wh transformation, and 4) do transformation.

1. Q the student past answer det- wh questions
2. Q the wife present can bake NP- wh

Q.6 Answer either A or B of the following questions: (10 Marks)

A What are the transformational processes in Transformational Grammar? Explain with examples.

B. Give the deep structure of the following sentences using tree diagrams (TWO only)

1. Listen to me.
2. Yesterday, I didn't know her address.
3. Someone was telling me a story.

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

Al- Salam University College
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Fourth Class
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Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Identify the three schools of Grammar and explain one of them.(10 Marks)

Q.2 Draw tree diagrams of the following sentences: (10 Marks)

1. My neighbour has seen the dog.
2. John could have been running this morning.

Q.3 Give the formulas of the following sentences, then add or delete as required between brackets, and write the resulting sentences: (10 Marks)

1. I ate then. (add be+ ing)
2. You could have been repairing the clock. (Delete be+ ing)
3. The waitress must be laughing at us. (Add have+ en)
4. We had gone to the window. (Delete have+ en)
5. I could see him well. (Delete can)

Q.4 Define the following terms in Transformational Grammar: (FIVE only)

(10 Marks)

1. PSR Phrase Structure Rules
2. TR Transformational Rules
3. PSTS Phrase Structure Terminal String
4. Concrete Nouns

5. Count Nouns
6. Competence
7. Performance
8. Intermediate Structure
9. Lexical Features
10. Lexicon

Q.5 Give the lexical features of the words underlined(nouns and verbs) in the following sentences: (FIVE only) (10 Marks)

1. Ali drives fast.
2. Mary put the book on the table.
3. The boy was lying on the floor.
4. The book dropped to the floor.
5. The ceiling leaks.
6. The camel is chewing the food.

Q.6 Give the deep structure of the following sentences using tree diagrams: (10 Marks)

1. Are you watching the clouds?
2. What did she want?
3. Don is not writing a letter.
4. We don't jump here.
5. The man is not ready now.

Q.7 Transform the following sentences into surface structures using tree diagrams: (10 Marks)

1. Q Bob will speak Adv p- wh
2. Q not he is going Adv r- wh
3. Q he wrote with NP- wh

4. Q not you have found det- wh book

5. Q she wanted NP- wh

Q.8 Answer either A or B: (10 Marks)

A. What are the four transformational processes in Transformational Grammar? Explain with examples and by using tree diagrams.

B. Transform the following sentences into surface structures using tree diagrams: (Five only)

1. Imp not you will close the door

2. I emailed a letter to my teacher (Indirect object movement)

3. I met my friend in this restaurant (Adverbial movement)

4. Q the bell present be ringing now

5. Q he present be saying NP- wh

6. Q not she arrived on time

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

Note: Answer FOUR questions only.

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences: (15 Points)

1. A sentence is
2. The is the name of your writing.
3. The paragraph is weak or bad if
4. A is a group of words that does not have a subject nor verb or it has either a subject or verb only.
5. A should be placed before the coordinators and, but, so and yet in coordinate sentences.

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences:

(15 Points)

1. A paragraph is strong or weak if it has
 - a. one topic sentence.
 - b. one idea.
 - c. one supporting sentence.
 - d. semi colon.
2. A sentence should start with a
 - a. capital letter.
 - b. full stop.
 - c. small letter.
 - d. semi colon.
3. The adjective can come before the, e.g. the brilliant students.
 - a. noun
 - b. verb
 - c. adverb
 - d. preposition

4. Brainstorming by free writing means you use

- a. words
- b. phrases
- c. short sentences
- d. long sentences

5. Peer reviewing means you hand your writing to your to check it for you.

- a. teacher
- b. father
- c. classmate
- d. neighbor

Q.3 Write true if the sentence is correct, and false if it is incorrect of each of the following sentences: (15 Points)

- 1. Each paragraph should have a topic, supporting and concluding sentences.
- 2. A topic sentence should be the last sentence of the paragraph
- 3. In checking, you check whether your writing has a title, sentences are related to the topic, etc.
- 4. The topic that explains the topic is called supporting sentences.
- 5. A simple sentence should consist of two sentences combined by and or but.

Q.4 Suggest a topic sentence and concluding sentence for the following paragraph: (15 Points)

Steps to Follow to Use ATM

..... First, you need to insert your card into the machine to begin transaction. Second, type in your PIN. This is typically 4 digits but can be longer. Third, choose a type of transaction. Fourth, enter the transaction amount. Fifth, select your receipt preference. Finally, take your card.

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe your favourite place. Your writing should be about 60 words in length. (15 Points)

Good Luck

Instructor: Alhan T. Najim

Note: Answer FOUR questions only.

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences:

1. There are six steps of writing. 1., 2., 3., 4., 5., and 6.
2. Margins means
3. A sentence should start with a and end with
4. There are four types of writing: 1., 2., 3., and 4.
5. The little boy looked so I went to comfort him.

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences:

1. A coordinate sentence means
 - a. summarizing the whole paragraph.
 - b. developing the whole paragraph.
 - c. telling the reader about the topic.
 - d. explaining the topic sentence.
2. Supporting sentences
 - a. develop your topic sentence.
 - b. restate your topic sentence.
 - c. summarize the whole paragraph.

d. tell the reader about the topic of the paragraph.

3. A paragraph is a group of sentences that talk about one certain

a. idea

b. phrase

c. topic

d. sentence

4. A concluding sentence is the sentence that

a. develops the topic sentence

b. summarize the paragraph

c. explains the topic sentence

restate the topic sentence

5. capitalization is used with

a. proper nouns

b. coordinators

c. articles

d. demonstratives

Q.3 Write true if the sentence is correct, and false if it is incorrect of each of the following sentences:

1. A paragraph is a group of sentences that talks about many topics.

2. Title means the space you leave from both sides of your writing.

3. The descriptive paragraph tells events in a certain place and time.
4. A comma comes at the end of a sentence.
5. A simple sentence should consist of one subject and one verb.

Q.4 State whether the following paragraph is a good or bad one and give reasons for your answer:

Why do People Lie?

One reason why people lie is to achieve personal power. Achieving personal power is helpful for someone who pretends that he is more confident than he really is. For example, my friend asked me to show him my car. At that time, I did not have any car because I sold it. This is why I asked my cousin to lend me his. When I showed him my cousin's car, I felt confident but embarrassed in front of my friend but I looked down on myself. Even if lying achieves power and confidence, I decided since then not to do so.

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe ONE of the following topics:

- 1. your favourite book,**
- 2. your favourite dish,**

Your writing should be about 60 words in length.

Brainstorm and write a descriptive paragraph on a lucky object, e.g. an object that you think brings luck to your life. Your writing should be no more than 60 words in length.

Note: Answer FOUR questions only.

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 - a. noun
 - b. verb
 - c. adverb
 - d. preposition

4. Brainstorming by free writing means you use

- a. words
- b. phrases
- c. short sentences
- d. long sentences

5. Peer reviewing means you hand your writing to your to check it for you.

- a. teacher
- b. father
- c. classmate
- d. neighbor

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..... .

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe ONE of the following topics:

1. your favourite place

2. you favourite person

Your writing should be about 60 words in length.

Brainstorm and write a descriptive paragraph on a piece of art you like, e.g. painting or sculpture. Your writing should be no more than 60 words in length.

Al- Salam University College
English Department
Third Class
Subject: Structural Grammar

2016/ 2017
Final Exam
Time: 3 Hours
Teacher: Alhan Tariq

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Show the immediate constituents of the following words: (10 Marks)

1. lifelessness
2. gentlemanly
3. cheerful
4. uncomfortable
5. itemized

Q.2 Identify whether the suffixes of the words underlined are ed-verbal, ed-adjectival, ing nominal, ing verbal, ing adjectival, er repetition, er noun, or er comparative (10 Marks)

1. You should read the printed statement.
2. A worried look crossed his face.
3. Old sayings are often half true.
4. A moving elephant is a picture of grace.
5. It was a charming spot.
6. The fighter weighed 100 kgs.
7. The jabber of voices came through the open door.
8. This is a heavier tennis racket than I want.

Q.3 Give the verb forms from the following adjectives: (10 Marks)

1. ripe
2. safe
3. solemn
4. solid
5. idol

Q.4 Show the grammatical structures that imply the following compound words: (10 Marks)

1. quicksand
2. outgo
3. treetop
4. stay- at- home
5. earthquake

Q.5 Give an example for each of the following word formation processes: (10 Marks)

1. reduplication
2. compounding
3. acronymy
4. clipping
5. derivation

Q.6 Underline the part of speech(structure class) in the following sentences: (10 Marks)

1. You are too tired.
2. I feel quite fine, thank you.

3. George sat between the two deans.

4. His is the best plan.

5. I think I can help you.

Good Luck

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Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Show the immediate constituents of the following words: (10 Marks)

1. helpless
2. embodiment
3. unlawful
4. reimbursements
5. preprofessional

Q.2 Identify whether the words underlined in the following sentences are compound or grammatical structures: (10 Marks)

1. Jim's new car is a hardtop.
2. she has a strong hold on him.
3. George found his father- in- law.
4. Henry is a designing teacher. (designing is with rising- falling intonation, teacher with falling rising intonation)
5. They bought it on the black market.

Q.3 Indicate the process of word formation represented by each of the following words: (10 Marks)

1. administration
2. tick- tick
3. hiss

4. OPEC

5. smog

Q.4 Derive nouns from the following words: (10 Marks)

1. help

2. complain

3. wise

4. friend

5. contemplate

6. accept

7. coward

8. piano

9. true

10. violent

Q.5 Write grammatical sentences with the following: (10 Marks)

1. compound preposition

2. periphrastic auxiliary do

3. substitute noun

4. a qualifier that modifies an adjective

5. an article

Q.6 Show the number of morphemes each of the following words contain: (10 Marks)

1. unforgettable

2. enlargement

3. malformations

4. refertilize

5. started

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim